
The Importance of Developing and Standardizing Gamete, Embryo and Larvae Handling in Aquatic Animals

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Artificial reproduction in aquatic animals usually involves the collection and handling of gametes both from males and females in a way that secures their quality and optimizes the fertilization event. There are innumerable specie-specific or family-specific protocols along the different aquatic species that inhabit from freshwater lagoons to seawater oceans. In that sense, this special issue gathers high-quality papers addressing different areas focused on gamete collection and handling, gamete storage (both short- and long-term storage), *in vitro* fertilization techniques, embryo development studies, and larvae management of different aquatic animals.

Whether our final goal is the advancement of basic research, aquaculture exploitation or biodiversity conservation, exploring aquatic organism's factors like seasonal spawning, type and strategy of reproduction, spawning induction, gamete extraction, fertilization factors, quality of the gametes and proper incubation of the larvae are key factors to enable our studies [1,2]. Due to the variability on those factors between taxa and even species-specific methods need to be developed and shared in the scientific community.

When dealing with sessile organisms that present external fertilization like, oysters such as *Crassostrea virginica* [3] or clams like *Mesodesma donacium* [4], animals not always have to be induced spawning. Mature gonads can sometimes be stripped and the gametes can then be collected directly like the case for oysters, although not always there are some species that present smaller size or internal fertilization. Spawning of clams or mussels have to be induced, and several spawning inductors have been used along the years, from overfeeding, to tide simulation or temperature shocks [5]. In all cases, protocols need to be established, shared and standardized within the scientific community to obtain gametes from different mollusks successfully. This is also the case with sea urchins, as they present external fertilization. Sea urchins are model organisms and therefore some species of sea urchins like *Strongylocentrotus purpuratus* or *Paracentrotus lividus* are quite well studied and with many protocols in place, but this is not the case of other sea urchins [6], as it can be seen that in many cases protocols would have to be adapted to particular species. Important knowledge about reproduction is often not well-known or standardized such as contact time, egg:sperm ratio, optimum parameters for embryo incubation, and expected outcome after larval rearing that are key information points for marine invertebrates [2,6].

When dealing with marine and freshwater fish, we have also a wide diversity of reproductive strategies [7]. Most of them share the external fertilization, where gametes from both males and females are released into the aquatic environment. These gametes will be a crucial/essential/key factor to achieve successful fertilization and hatching rates throughout the *in vitro* fertilization trials [1]. For releasing gametes, fish broodstock must be properly matured, and some environmental factors like salinity, photoperiod and/or temperature can stimulate the sperm and oocyte production [8]. In other many cases, these factors are not optimal, and it is necessary to apply of short or long hormonal treatments in species with reproductive bottlenecks [9,10]. Once collected male and female gametes, it will be essential to keep their quality using extenders at different ratios [11], and/or adding antibiotics for the fertilization trials. Finally, the choice of egg:sperm ratio is also an essential factor which needs to be considered to standardize and optimize the *in vitro* fertilization trials on the aquaculture sector. Generally, an excess of sperm is used in *in vitro* fertilization trials both in freshwater and seawater species, but an appropriate combination of the number of spermatozoa per oocyte must be used in order to enhance the reproductive efficiency in fish farms and to avoid wasting sperm when available gametes are limited [12].

Beyond theoretical considerations, an emphasis was placed on a wide range of factors studied to determine proper protocols for handling, spawning and reproducing a wide range of different species in different taxa. Further investigation is required to refine the protocols and to extend them to other species whenever possible, nonetheless the contributions of this special issue will provide further insights regarding these different aspects, while promoting new investigations targeting the standardized and successful reproduction of aquatic animals.

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